

Additional file 4: Figure S3.a Graphical compilation of likelihood ratio profiles calculated for each chromosome (1cM interval) for RESISTANCE after the injection challenge

Additional file 4: Figure S3.b Graphical compilation of likelihood ratio profiles calculated for each chromosome (1cM interval) for STATUS after the injection challenge

Additional file 4: Figure S3.c Graphical compilation of likelihood ratio profiles calculated for each chromosome (1cM interval) for RESISTANCE after the immersion challenge

Additional file 4: Figure S3.d Graphical compilation of likelihood ratio profiles calculated for each chromosome (1cM interval) for STATUS after the immersion challenge